

Abstract**Predictive Value of Transvaginal Endometrial Thickness Measurement in Postmenopausal Bleeding in Kano**

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Background: Postmenopausal bleeding (PMB) is one of the common presentations of endometrial pathology. Transvaginal endometrial thickness, a less invasive test, can be the initial screening test for evaluating endometrial pathology in these women, in order to determine those who will require an endometrial biopsy. The aim of this study was to determine the predictive value of transvaginal endometrial thickness measurement in the evaluation of endometrial pathology among women with PMB in Kano.

Materials and Method: It was a cross-sectional multicenter study of women with PMB that had endometrial thickness measurement using a 6.5MHZ transvaginal transducer and an endometrial sample by suction curettage and subjected to histopathologic diagnosis.

Results: Forty-five women were evaluated. The mean age of the patients was 58.2 ± 6.0 years, the mean parity was 4.4 ± 1.9 , the mean age at menopause was 51.3 ± 1.4 years, and the mean duration from menopause to symptom was 6.9 ± 4.9 years. Nineteen (42.2%) of patients had endometrial hyperplasia, with 10 (52.6%) being simple hyperplasia and 9 (47.4%) atypical hyperplasia. Endometrial cancer was found in 12 (26.7%), while 14 (31.1%) had normal histology. Transvaginal endometrial thickness of 5mm cut-off was found to have a sensitivity of 87.1%, specificity 50%, positive predictive value 79.4%, negative predictive value of 63.6% and diagnostic accuracy of 75.6%.

Conclusion: Transvaginal endometrial thickness at a cut-off value of 5mm correlated well with histopathologic diagnosis of endometrial pathology. Therefore, it should be the first line test in the evaluation of women with postmenopausal bleeding in Kano.

Keywords: Endometrial thickness, Biopsy, Postmenopausal bleeding

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